

Exporting the Chinese School: How Convincing is the Relational Theory of World Politics as Formulated by Yaqing Qin?

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Abstract

Does a theory rooted in Confucian thought have intellectual value beyond its cultural origin? A consistent charge advanced by critics to challenge the credibility of Relational Theory (RT), as posited by Qin Yaqing, pertains to its scarce applicability beyond Confucian cultural spaces. This paper defends Qin's Relational Theory against such charges, proposing that Qin's Relational Theory of International Relations is convincing insofar as (1) explaining social phenomena beyond its alleged cultural departure point and (2) offering answers to policy questions that dominant theories in the current Western scholarship cannot. By exporting Qin's relational theory outside of its Confucian cultural birthplace and identifying spaces RT has been engaged with as a viable international relations (IR) theory, this paper finds that RT has the capacity to fill empirical gaps in the explanatory capacity of existing IR theories via their ontological differences—namely, Constructivism (as RT's Western comparison), English School (as a fellow theory charged with indigenization), and Liberal Feminism (as another relational approach). This paper contributes to the theoretical literature on RT by setting the ontological groundwork for re-evaluating persistent policy problems that mainstream IR has yet to fully account for.

Keywords: Relational Theory, relationality, Confucianism, Chinese School, Hegelian philosophy, *zhongyong* dialectic

Introduction

Mainstream International Relations (IR) theory has tended to appeal to similar notions posited in Rudyard Kipling's adage: "East is East, and West is West, and never the twain shall meet" (Kipling, 1899, p. 5). Calls for Asian universalism have flooded the post-colonial literature on IR theory, challenging understandings of non-Western theories as indigenous and the "worlding" of Western mainstream IR (Spivak, 1985, p. 247). Others have suggested that Asian IR better explains cultural specificity rather than posing as a form of scientific universalism (Kang, 2012). These discussions are of particular relevance in assessing the cogence of Qin Yaqing's "Relational Theory of World Politics" of the Chinese School of IR (Qin, 2018). Does a theory rooted in Confucian thought have intellectual value outside of its cultural origin?

The Relational Theory of World Politics, formulated by Qin Yaqing, is a theory of IR that takes relations as its ontological and analytical referent point, taking meaning from human practice (Qin, 2016, pp. 33–47). That is to say, it assumes individuals, states, and international institutions are the product of relations, rather than isolated substances, to account for behavior in international relations. By extension, it therefore troubles the dominant Hegelian dialectic that is so prevalent in Western international relations theory, which views the individual (and by extension, states) as a self-contained and pre-constituted actor that then interacts with others (Raspa, 2016).

Underpinning Relational Theory is three primary assumptions. IR is a realm of interrelatedness between entities; these actors are thus always relationally co-constitutive; relations are always in motion i.e. amenable to change (Qin, 2016, pp. 36–37). Human practice, and by extension states, are informed by the totality of their relational

spheres. Orienting Relational Theory towards this theoretical position is its Confucian cultural origin, and more specifically, the *zhongyong* dialectics (中庸), which emphasizes inclusivity, complementation, and harmony (Qin, 2016, pp.152–194). This involves polarities as co-theses rather than the anti-thesis found in Western, Hegelian philosophy that emphasizes non-contradiction through rationality (Qin, 2016, pp. 153–169). Thus, harmony is the natural organizing logic of IR, rather than anarchy and conflict through differences in rationalist approaches such as neorealism (Zhao, 2009). Despite its Confucian founding, Qin does not intend for the theory to be indigenized. Indeed, whilst relationality is most evident in Confucian communities, imbricating relational spheres are ubiquitous in IR. Qin proposes that Relational Theory is to be exported beyond its cultural and geographical birthplace (Qin, 2016, p.45).

The most common criticism of Relational Theory pertains to its scarce applicability beyond Confucian spaces. Choi (2022) addresses the apparent essentialist framing of Chinese cultural identity in Qin’s theory, suggesting that equating relationality strictly with Confucian traditions risks oversimplifying cultural dynamics and may hinder the theory’s universal applicability. This is one of several factors turned to when discussing the credibility problem of Relational Theory. Others include how convincing the relational ontology is in comparison with rationalist positions, and how Qin’s theory departs from other forms of relational theorizing such as post-colonial and feminist approaches. Due to scope, this paper deals with one of these questions—the traveling capability of Qin’s Relational Theory—to assess its cogence.

This paper argues that Qin’s Relational Theory is convincing, as it can explain social phenomena beyond its cultural departure point. Indeed, it can offer answers to policy questions that dominant theories in the

current Western scholarship *cannot*. This will be exemplified through a critical analysis of its theoretical assumptions in conjunction with its ability to fill empirical gaps in the explanatory capacity of existing theories—Constructivism (as Relational Theory’s Western comparison), English School (as a fellow theory charged with indigenization), and Western Feminism (as an approach critiqued for its universalism). To operationalize “convincing,” the explanatory capacity of Relational Theory will be evaluated on two criteria. Firstly, what the author’s ambitions for the theory are. Qin intends to offer a lens for understanding the world beyond Confucian cultural communities (Zalewski, 1996, pp. 340–353). If Qin Yaqing insists the theory is not limited to Confucian settings, and one of its primary charges is its cultural particularism, the theory must *travel* well (Kang, 2012; Qin, 2018). Secondly, as an external measure of success, Cox (1981) argues that a theory has utility if it allows us to see the world differently. That is to say, it does not simply describe what fits the dominant model of thinking. To prove this, this paper asks whether Relational Theory offers analytical advantages over Constructivism, English School, and Liberal Feminism in understanding policy questions.

Through a critical analysis of Relational Theory’s theoretical counterparts, this paper evaluates its explanatory power relative to other theories that dominate the theoretical space. In doing so, this paper highlights what impact Relational Theory can make as a viable theory of international relations that offers something the theories identified above cannot. This paper will not be measuring how convincing Relational Theory is based on assessments within mainstream American IR, given that the inclusion of theories in this space is contingent on its development of cause-effect arguments under rationalist thought, thus making for biased analysis (Hoffmann, 1977, pp. 212–241). Rather, this paper references less-obvious spaces Relational Theory has been engaged with to testify to the attention it has received as a viable IR theory.

Due to scope, the paper also does not seek to evaluate the internal coherence of Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory. The existing literature has laid the necessary conceptual groundwork for further inquiry into the theory's utility, by establishing its foundational coherence (Guzzini, 2024; Kavalski, 2017; Qin, 2016, 2018).

The following three sections represent the main analysis. The literature review outlines how Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory of World Politics has mainly been primarily engaged conceptually with limited empirical application, particularly beyond Confucian cultural contexts. The theory and methods outlines Relational Theory and introduces how the lexicon of postcolonial feminist insights can articulate a critique of mainstream theories. This section also sets the criteria for what makes a theory "convincing"—explanatory power, critical depth, and practical utility. It sets the basis to explore the primary research question in the main analysis, which demonstrates the theory's empirical value through case studies like the EU's Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) and rule-of-law disputes, revealing how relational logics can explain political behavior in non-Confucian settings where Western theories fall short.

1. Literature Review

The existing literature on Qin's Relational Theory has largely prioritized its conceptual clarity over empirical veracity. While understandable—conceptual clarity and internal consistency are essential to lay the groundwork for further critical engagement with its utility, it has hitherto remained underdeveloped beyond this point. This has denied Relational Theory its due diligence. Much of the literature can be divided into roughly two groups:- (1) conceptual and (2) practical engagement with the theory.

The conceptual literature has typically focused on the extent to which Relational Theory offers an internally coherent alternative to its Western counterparts—by introducing Confucian concepts to the study of international relations, it challenges the ontological individualism of mainstream Western approaches. It does so by emphasizing relationality as the foundational model of social being (Jiang, 2018; Nordin and Smith, 2018; Qin, 2016, 2018). While useful in laying the essential conceptual groundwork from which to develop the theory, its empirical engagement is comparatively weaker. Qin's theory introduced an entirely new lexicon of conceptualizing international relations, which requires significant attention: a theory is of little use until (1) its empirical applicability is proven and (2) it can offer something different to what existing theories purport to account for (Cox, 1981). Stefano Guzzini (2024) seeks to reconcile the imbalance in the literature between theoretical discussion and empirical engagement by critically examining Qin's attempt to explain relationalism at four levels of analysis (ontological, theoretical, interpretative, and strategic). Guzzini argues that while admirable, Qin's attempt to cover *all* four levels of analysis makes for limited explanatory capacity (Guzzini, 2024). Guzzini argues that despite this, the relational theoretical aspect of the theory remains valuable for understanding the co-constitution of identities and interests through interactions (Guzzini, 2024). Guzzini thus applied Qin's vision of open, trust-based diplomacy to study the Helsinki Accords, deeming it a prime example of true multilateralism which embodied a foreign policy strategy aimed at transforming adversarial international relations into a productive partnership (Guzzini, 2024). While holding significant merit in its deviation from the oft-insular approach in the existing literature, Guzzini's empirical engagement is tied to outdated examples that provide minimal insight into contemporary international relations. As Qin articulates a vision for a relational world order today, that is, an order focused on the mutual influence of, and thus governing of *relations among interconnected actors*, rather than actors

as isolated entities, critical engagement with his theory requires a commitment to proving its contemporary relevance (Qin, 2016, 2018).

The literature which attempts to export Relational Theory is scarce. This literature tends to prematurely reconcile the theory with Western theoretical concepts before giving it due diligence, suggesting that its Confucian-based lexicon inherently Sinicizes the theory, reproducing a form of cultural essentialism (Callahan, 2008). As a result, its universal applicability is undermined by its reliance on culturally reliant assumptions (Callahan, 2008). Such literature assumes that taking Relational Theory seriously requires a complete overhaul of the current international order. However, while engagement with the theory requires critical engagement with complex concepts, it challenges it without requiring a wholesale replacement of the existing order.

While acknowledging this work's contribution to articulating a global IR, this paper argues that the existing literature on Relational Theory has yet to produce a study solely dedicated to demonstrating the empirical applicability of Qin's Relational Theory beyond its cultural origins and assessing its distinct explanatory value.

2. Theory and Methods

2.1 Theory

This paper takes Qin's "Relational Theory of World Politics" as its ontological point of departure, which is supported by a critical post-colonial approach to understanding emancipation, to articulate a critique of the limits of Liberal Feminism. Qin's Relational Theory has yet to articulate a cohesive critique of contending IR theories. The lack of theoretical engagement limits Relational Theory's ability to carve out a distinct position in the existing theoretical landscape. Consequently, Relational Theory's embryonic

status, relative to other pervasive theories of IR, is not yet equipped with the adequate tools to critically engage with other theories. While engaging other theories may not be Qin's primary objective, doing so is essential for establishing Relational Theory as a viable alternative in IR.

To strengthen its critical footing, this paper draws on Postcolonial Feminism to articulate the limitations of Liberal Feminism. In doing so, this does not suggest the limitations of Relational Theory as a theory in isolation. Rather, this paper acknowledges that the Postcolonial Feminist critique offers the most compelling and comprehensive framework for exposing the limitations of Liberal Feminism, while Relational Theory can offer something unique by providing the lexicon of the *tianxia* worldview, which can provide a measure of good governance as the ability to effectively manage relations between entities.

This paper draws on Mohanty's critique of the "othering" inherent in Western feminist discourse, which often marginalizes non-Western visions of emancipation (Mohanty, 1988). In other words, Western feminism, shaped largely by Liberal Feminist thinking, which focuses on individual rights and equality within existing systems rather than challenging those systems—it is both dependent on and reinforces a rights-based vision of emancipation. This vision limits the way emancipation is understood, keeping it confined within a state-centered framework. Liberal Feminism thus renders itself void of a truly transnational definition of liberation by universalizing a highly context-specific form of oppression. Hence, this paper equips itself with a Postcolonial Feminist approach to articulate more inclusive concepts of emancipation and reveal the limitations of the dominant Liberal Feminism (Parashar, 2016).

This paper defines "convincing" based on what the theory sets out to achieve, drawing from Zalewski's framework on how theory functions in IR (Zalewski, 1996). This paper maintains that Qin Yaqing endeavors to offer an alternative lens

for understanding the world outside of its Confucian cultural origin—theory as explanation (Zalewski, 1996). It also functions to trouble the fixed, static, and binary-focused ontological assumptions of mainstream (Western) IR—*theory as critique* (Zalewski, 1996). Finally, relational theorizing itself constitutes a practice of world-making, in that by adopting a relational understanding, political practice can move toward harmony and dynamic equilibrium, rather than assuming a predisposition to balance of power politics—*theory as practice* (Zalewski, 1996). Thus, to satisfy this criterion of “convincing,” this paper uses Relational Theory to exemplify how it offers an alternative understanding of IR that not only deviates from, but troubles the assumptions underpinning the Hegelian dialectic. It also indicates how Relational Theory operates to not only explain but *inform* political practice.

2.2 Methods

To prove that Relational Theory satisfies the criterion of “convincing” outlined above, this paper identifies instances of policy decision-making at the international and state level (excluding states shaped by Confucian cultural communities), assuming that international institutions are, at least to a large extent, the sum of their relations (Wendt, 1999). Rather than conducting interviews with policymakers, this analysis uses publicly available documents, policy statements, and foreign policy decisions. This methodological choice reflects the theoretical orientation of the paper: Relational Theory emphasizes the dynamics and patterns of interaction among actors, which are often more legible in formal articulations of policy and institutional behavior than through individual perspectives. Reinforcing this, as Relational Theory seeks to understand the logic and structure of relationships rather than subjective motivations of actors, the procedural outputs of states and institutions appear the most appropriate empirical sites.

Supporting the definitional criteria of “convincing” as outlined in the Theory section, this paper strictly refers to less conspicuous areas in which Relational Theory has been applied to highlight the growing recognition it has garnered as a credible theoretical framework. This methodological framework ultimately serves as an external measure of Relational Theory’s success as a cogent theory, which isn’t defined solely by the terms delineated by its author.

To clarify, this paper does not seek to validate the persuasiveness of Relational Theory through its reception within the positivist IR scholarship. Given that the literature is largely grounded in rational-choice models of thinking, often overlooking the centrality of identity and culture in international relations, such an approach would risk analytical bias. That is to say, the paper’s methodological framework would rely on evaluations from scholars who are, by disciplinary orientation, already predisposed to frameworks rooted in the very intellectual tradition that Relational Theory troubles. The paper testifies to the theory’s plausibility and analytical utility by examining its resonance within less conventional or peripheral contexts. If Relational Theory is to hold any explanatory capacity, then its main tenets should be observable within these referents. The following comprises the main analysis.

3. Main Analysis

3.1 “Politics As The Art Of Coexistence”: Understanding The Limitations Of The EU CFSP Relationally

Qin’s Relational Theory can best exemplify its empirical and theoretical value by offering answers to critical research questions left unanswered in Constructivism’s understandings of EU security identity. During the 1990s, Constructivism provided an indispensable shift in approaches to EU governance analysis that seemingly departed from the rationalist approach stressing neo-functionalism and fixed preferences as a materially-based ontology

(Pollack, 2005, pp. 357–98). By emphasizing the dynamic social construction of state interests, identities, and norms, Constructivism highlights how shared ideas, discourse, and institutional norms can shape integration dynamics within institutions (Checkel, 1998). This distinguished itself from existing neo-functional approaches that stressed fixed state preferences and integration driven by “functional spillover”—that integration in one area necessitates integration in others (Nicoli, 2019).

More specifically, it provided interpretive approaches to the development of the EU’s CFSP as a security community by taking the maintenance of global norms and identity as ontologically significant in human behavior (Adler and Barnett, 1998, pp. 3–28). However, in emphasizing the communicative pathway of norms formed by international organizations and transmitted to individual actors, constructivism remains divorced from, and negligent of, theoretical frameworks that stress relationality *between* institutions. As a result, Constructivism has been unable to explain why the CFSP has fallen short of delivering a cohesive EU foreign policy through a shared security identity, if by taking normative rationality as the basis for human action, the most probable outcome would be so.

Norm-based constructivist approaches assume that what motivates human action is a “logic of appropriateness”—actors internalize understandings of what is socially designated as “true,” “right,” or “good,” and make decisions based on what satisfies this criterion (March & Olsen, 1998, p. 949). This does not necessarily render relations unimportant in human decision-making, nor should it be suggested that the “logic of appropriateness” does not inform human action (March & Olsen, 1998). However, this paper maintains that if the *primary* motivation for human action is an assessment of the normative appropriateness of taking a particular action, then one would

expect the EU’s CFSP to have achieved greater coherence and cohesion. In this view, Member States would be inclined to support a unified foreign policy because regional cooperation is largely perceived as normatively legitimate (Jupille et al., 2003). Why does an effective EU common foreign policy find itself stymied?

This paper maintains that Qin’s Relational Theory offers answers to these questions emerging from constructivist approaches to EU security. Qin argues that examining the connate imbrication of multiple relational circles as the basis for action can offer useful insights into the barriers to, and opportunities for, cooperation within institutions (Qin, 2018). The logic of relationality, an alternative to the logic of appropriateness, assumes two things—firstly, that actors are both enabled and restrained by the totality of their relational circles (Qin, 2016, p. 38). Actions in one relational circle can modify the context in which a decision is made, influencing which course of action appears more rational or favorable than another. Absent of their relational context, an actor has little basis to ascertain what is rational and what is not. Secondly, actors use their relational circles to pursue their self-interests, and view their relational circles as a means to satisfy them (Qin, 2016, p. 38–39). In other words, if an actor’s needs in a particular realm are satisfied by a relational circle, it will not necessarily pursue it in another. The logic of relationality can apply directly to the EU’s CFSP to account for its shortcomings.

That is to say, the barriers to common EU foreign policy reside in an enduring condition in which EU members are unwilling to dedicate further resources to the CFSP when their security, in both status and materiality, is already accounted for nationally and through other security organizations such as NATO. The CFSP currently has no authority to impose an impetus for action on individual states—policy decisions are initiated either nationally or through unanimity in the Council of the European Union (Denza, 2002, p. 121). As a result, most states (22 out of 27 EU states are also a part of NATO), recognizing

the collective of their relational circles as comprising a robust security identity, are unwilling to dedicate themselves to common EU foreign policy, when institutions such as NATO offer the same security identity through territorial defense and peacekeeping that the CFSP offers.

An alternative interpretation within the literature highlights that Constructivism hasn't failed to explain the lack of cohesion in EU foreign policy, but instead indicates that a fragmented or evolving European identity explains the difficulty in forming a united CFSP (Arkan, 2014). Theorists such as Thomas Risse-Kappen (2010) contend that as the European identity is formed through public discourse and socialization within and across EU Member States, it is so amenable to change that the CFSP's weakness merely reflects an enduring identity struggle among EU members, rather than a theoretical shortcoming of Constructivism. While this paper acknowledges such counter-arguments, it does not change the enduring condition in which Constructivism struggles to divorce itself from a rationalist, agency-driven worldview. That is to say, despite the Constructivist critique of theories undergirded by a rationalist ontology, much of the Constructivist literature still operates within the same representational logic, in which the individual is seen as an autonomous agent, and the system is structured by utility-maximizing behavior, even when couched in norm-following terms (Price & Reus-Smit, 1998).

Relational Theory is vulnerable to the charge that in this particular case, EU states "maximize utility" by opting against further integration into the CFSP, thus situating itself within a rationalist ontology. To clarify, Relational Theory does not deny that actors do not act in accordance with self-interest, nor does it deny the "self" as significant. Rather, Relational Theory assumes that an individual's understanding of its self-interest is, to a larger extent than is assumed under rationalist

logics, by the totality of its relational circles (Guzzini, 2024). Such arguments conflate acting in self-interest with a commitment to a rationalist ontology. Rather, Relational Theory can provide an alternative lens for understanding the ideational framework in which one makes choices by conceptualizing the self as constituted through relations with others.

Relational Theory can offer a different interpretation of policy issues that accounts for social phenomena based on the interaction between *relational circles*. In this particular example of the CFSP, it provides an alternative framework for understanding its limitations. Qin's emphasis on relational circles as ontologically significant in decision-making answers existing calls in the intellectual space to recognize the centrality of inter-institutional relationships in IR. It also answers empirical questions that have troubled the policy realm since the Constructivist-led "governance turn" in EU analysis (Berenskoetter, 2007, pp. 647–676). As a result, Relational Theory provides a theoretical alternative that deviates from a Constructivist orientation towards the logic of normative rationality, by offering an account of relational context as preceding rational social action (Qin and Nordin, 2019, pp. 601–614). What Qin's Relational Theory ultimately provides is a convincing account of the relationship between relationality and social action that can (1) not only apply to policy questions beyond its Confucian birthplace but (2) answer policy questions relating to CFSP that has troubled Constructivism that existing (Western) theories cannot. This is a significant testament to its cogence.

3.2 Responding To Barry Buzan And Jiangli Wang—Exporting The Chinese School

Similar to the English School, Qin's Relational Theory has been criticized for its inability to travel beyond its cultural origin. Martha Finnemore argues that the lack of engagement of American IR with the English School is a result of its remote proximity to positivist

methodologies—given that the English School and Relational Theory renounce cause-effect hypotheses, similar explanations can be attributed to Relational Theory’s marginalization (Finnemore, 2001). Wang and Buzan (2014, pp.1–43) outline multiple charges the English School faces that Qin’s Relational Theory should avoid as a newer IR theory—of most concern is that the English School has offered weak accounts of IR at the regional level. Indeed, in its focus on “international” or “world” typologies of “system” and “society,” the ES provides little on how regionalism can shape such phenomena. Ironically too, the ES also offers an account of such typologies that are inherently regionalized through its account of primary institutions as rooted in the warring, international law and balance of power of the 17th/18th centuries in Europe (Stivachtis, 2014, pp. 109–126). Whilst these charges of indigenization against the English School are valid, the same cannot be said for Relational Theory. Indeed, Relational Theory can offer more to Western regional policy than the ES can offer reciprocally.

Relational Theory insulates itself from criticisms that it only produces an Asia-specific account of IR, by offering a regional account through its emphasis on the complementation of opposing entities (Qin, 2018, p.178). Complementation, one of the founding principles underpinning the *zhongyong* dialectic, which Relational Theory takes as its epistemological and methodological foundation, refers to the dynamic interplay between actions in the international system, where relationships are characterized by mutual adaptation and co-evolution (Qin, 2016). The concept aligns with one interpretation of Confucianism—the ideal of harmony, in which balance is achieved not through uniformity but through the integration of differences (Qin, 2024). Under the *zhongyong* dialectic, harmony is taken as the basic and natural state of nature, and conflict as the exception (Babones, 2017; Qin, 2024).

A charge often waged against Qin’s Relational Theory suggests it cannot account for subject/object relationships and by extension, the power differential between the two, meaning Relational Theory undermines the role of power dynamics in shaping international relations (Guzzini, 2024). However, assuming that one can only assess a theory based on what it purports to do, rather than what it does not, such a charge reads Relational Theory through the very dichotomous lens that the *zhongyong* dialectic refutes. Relational Theory’s emphasis on the complementation of opposing entities can account for spaces in IR where conflicts of interest have laid the groundwork for productive partnerships.

For example, the EU’s evolving relationship with Hungary and Poland amid ongoing rule-of-law disputes between 2020 and 2023 illustrates a complementary assimilation of differing strategic priorities between opposing entities. From 2020 to 2023, Hungary and Poland faced criticism and legal action from EU institutions over policies that undermined judicial independence, media freedom, and democratic standards (Kos, 2023). Rather than leading to a decisive rupture of ties, the EU’s response was marked by a dynamic process of negotiation and incremental adaptation—namely, the Rule-of-Law Conditionality Mechanism, which tied access to EU funds to compliance with core democratic norms (Baraggia & Bonelli, 2022). While Hungary and Poland resisted this conditionality, suggesting it challenged its national sovereignty, the EU withheld certain budgetary disbursements while simultaneously maintaining open channels for legal and political dialog (Baraggia & Bonelli, 2022). In response, both the EU, and Hungary and Poland, made concessions—the EU refined the scope of conditionality, while Hungary and Poland executed partial reforms and made amendments sufficient to unlock portions of the funds.

Such an example bears a strong resemblance to the complementary relationship between opposing entities as posited by Qin’s Relational

Theory, in which difference can be the basis for the “dynamic reproduction” of a complementary relationship (Qin, 2018, p.178). That is to say, differing strategic interests between the EU and Poland and Hungary were renegotiated to achieve mutual benefit. Rather than operating within a rigid framework of compliance or punishment, both sides engaged in an iterative process of dialog, which reasoned through relational balance (integration, rather than elimination, of difference) (Qin, 2016, 2018). Understood through the lens of Relational Theory, the EU’s concessions are not indicators of a breakdown of norms, nor institutional weakness, but a relational system in which actors co-evolve through conflict. That is to say, in accordance with the *zhongyong* perspective, harmony arises not through uniformity but through the respectful integration of difference.

This indicates that Qin’s Relational Theory can offer more comprehensive insights into the relational and regional dynamics of states extraneous from Confucian culture. Where policy analysts have doggedly focused on conflicts of interest in commentary on the long-running rule of law dispute between the EU, and Poland and Hungary, there is complementation and harmony to be found that makes for a productive partnership. This example exemplifies that Qin’s Relational Theory can offer an account of relationalism that considers the complementation of competing interests and its prospects for regional dynamic developments, as opposed to the focus of the English School on “world” or “international” orientations. Compounding this, the theory’s conceptual flexibility, notably its foundational principle of mutual adaptation through difference, Relational Theory can offer a more appropriate conceptual framework for both understanding and facilitating processes of conflict resolution, mediation, and reconciliation. This is a significant testament to its ability to travel beyond its cultural origins, and offer more than current Western IR.

3.3 Globalizing A Regional Project - How Do Other Relational Theories Fair?

Assessments of the cogence of Qin’s Relational Theory and its usefulness for the study of IR ultimately necessitate a discussion of its utility vis-à-vis other forms of relational theorizing, to determine if Qin’s Relational Theory offers a unique lens. Relational Theory can help advance an intellectual project of universal emancipation where other relational theories like Western feminism have engaged in intellectual processes of “othering” and other marginalized non-Western concepts of liberation. Spivak (1981, pp. 154–184) argues that Western Feminism has taken the rationality embedded in liberalism as its primary object of criticism to trouble the violence it has permitted against populations deemed a threat to civil order along ethno-gendered lines. This focus on critiquing the violence embedded in liberal epistemology as a dominant Liberal Feminist posture works to prioritize the Eurocentric experience and ultimately mobilizes it to generate understanding of how to emancipate *all* women. This is to the detriment of non-Western women whose issues with traditional institutions that marginalize and oppress them are not positivist by nature, but more frequently religious or cultural.

In fact, the lexicon of rights-based individuality has been valuable in many emancipatory feminist movements in the non-West. South Korea’s urban redevelopment projects of the 1980s under President Chun Doo-hwan displaced families residing in shantytowns who had largely moved from rural areas to developing cities in the 1960s (Shin, 2017). In the midst of a tumultuous dynamic between civic society and the authoritarian regime, women grew increasingly emboldened to engage in political forms of resistance. By 1987, women had formed the Seoul City Association of the Evacuated Urban Poor to address their grievances over being dislocated (Moon, 2002a, p. 482). Protest activity by the group was met with disapproval by the general public, seeing it as incongruous with the polite and quiet expectations of women (Moon, 2002b).

That said, when the KWAU, a prominent association of women's organizations, joined the National Federal of Nationalistic and Democratic Movements (NFNDM), a democracy-promoting association comprised primarily of men, KWAU were denounced for being too moderate in their approach to challenge entrenched political structures (Moon, 2002a, p.482). The women were fixed to a position where they were too radical for civil society's expectations of them, but too moderate to activist groups. The women's grievances with gender inequality were therefore not linked to the lexicon of democratic reform or rights-based discourse coming out of the Western liberal epistemology—to the contrary, it has emboldened them to find methods of resistance. Rather, their grievances rested in very cultural understandings of the expectations of women. Deeply rooted gender norms informed a highly masculinized civil society that still made it difficult for women to fully participate in public activism (Moon, 2002a, pp. 473–500). Thus, Western Feminism has engaged itself in an intimate relationship with colonial projects by universalizing a regionalized experience, at the expense of a transnational feminist vision.

The emphasis on the *tianxia* (天下) worldview and harmony in Qin's Relational Theory has potential to offer a truly transnational feminist interpretation of gender order (Qin, 2016). At its core, the *tianxia* worldview advances an understanding of world politics as capable of constituting "the exclusion of nothing and no one" (Feng, 2005, p. 109). Basing *tianxia* on the idea of human nature found in the *zhongyong* dialectic, no two entities are intrinsically antithetical, making the *tianxia* worldview a geographically expansive project. Further to this, as *tianxia's* focal point is relations, effective governance is recognized as the ability to manage relations between entities, to the extent that the state of relations can be viewed as harmonious amongst a polity. This helps advance a transnational feminist project

more so than Western Feminism in two ways. Firstly, where rules-based governance has been the primary target of criticism in Western feminism to challenge rights and laws, governance based on managing relations goes beyond this. Secondly, markers of failed governance are indicated by a failure to appropriately manage these relations, as opposed to conceptions of order as a law-abiding polity. Qin's Relational Theory can thus account for sites of epistemic and cultural violence against women, where Western Liberal Feminism has only been concerned with legal injustice against women. Relational Chinese IR thus makes a useful contribution, both to the transnational feminist vision that current relational thinking in the West doesn't offer, as well as more broadly helping to trouble exclusive West/non-West binary logics that have been reproduced by current IR theory (Acharya and Buzan, 2009). That is to say, Relational Theory's vision of harmony as the state of nature can not only provide a useful entry point into the theoretical incorporation of hitherto labeled non-West IR theories into the mainstream, but also the practical emancipation of a collective that is too often excluded by the Western vision of emancipatory success based on rights. In Qin's words, inclusivity is the route to transformative "progress, co-evolution, and sustainable order" (Qin, 2016, p. 45).

Conclusion

This paper has argued that Qin's Relational Theory offers a convincing account of world politics by wielding an explanatory capacity that (1) empirically transcends its cultural Confucian roots and (2) can offer explanations for policy questions that much of mainstream IR cannot. Firstly, Relational Theory can explain the limitations of the EU CFSP through a relational analysis *between* institutions that Constructivism doesn't offer. Secondly, Relational Theory gives a comprehensive account of regional dynamics between Western states where the English School pays little attention to regionalism. Thirdly, where other relational theories of IR, such as Liberal Feminism, universalize a culturally

specific project of emancipation that risks ignoring other forms of oppression, Relational Theory's vision of transnational feminism moves beyond the troubling of legal/institutional sites by recognizing cultural/religious violence. Qin's Relational Theory can make a significant contribution beyond its cultural origins, providing intellectual contributions that are indispensable to the mainstream IR canon. Much of the theoretical groundwork has been laid to convincingly testify to the internal cogence of Qin Yaqing's Relational Theory of World Politics (Acharya & Buzan, 2019; Nordin et al., 2019; Qin, 2016;). However, there remains significant scope to prove Relational Theory's explanatory capacity in the empirical realm. Although this paper provides an empirical illustration of Relational Theory's explanatory strengths, its scope is intentionally narrow, having to engage with both the theoretical/conceptual, and the empirical. Future research is needed to build on this foundation and fully explore the theory's broader applicability beyond its Confucian origin. Further inquiry into (1) the applicability of Qin's relational framework across diverse regional contexts, (2) how regional organizations reflect relational principles versus rule-based (liberal) structures, and if they do not, (3) how Qin's concept of harmony with difference can inform global governance models, particularly in relation to inter-state mediation. Only then, by paying Qin's Relational Theory due diligence, conditions for a global IR can begin to be satisfied (Acharya and Buzan, 2019, pp. 285–320).

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